

The Declaration of Independence

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Introduction

The Declaration of Independence is the founding document of the United States of America (USA). The Continental Congress of the British colonies in North America adopted the Declaration in Independence Hall in Philadelphia on July 4, 1776. The document proclaimed that the thirteen original colonies US were "free and independent states." It was the latest step in a long process that led the colonies to the final separation from Britain (Marshall, 1987).

The idea of the Declaration of Independence started to come in progress after the events of Imperial Reform, The British wanted to fix their debt finances; they created a tax reform, an idea of expanding their goods into America due to the British war of 1754-1763. The British military victory brought deployment in the north in 1763. In 1762, King George the 3rd wanted the British military's protection for his family, friends and the king's ministers. He was scared that the rebels were going to attack them (Barlow, 1996).

Discussion

The fact of the troops was costing the British significant amounts of money, soon after the war, The British national debt became incredibly worse from 75 million to 133 million pounds in debt. Due to the large debts and disputes between Britain, Canada and Indians, the treasury thought raising the taxes would be a huge problem solver. The British Prime Minister Lord Bute decided to raise taxes. He increased taxes on goods such as tobacco and sugar in addition to those with less political power such as middle class all the way down to the poor.

This tax increase would raise the cost to consumers, hopefully profiting money and decreasing the percentage of deep debt that Britain was experiencing (Wills, 2002).

The British government doubled the size of the tax bureaucracy. In 1767, Prime Minister Grenville demanded that Americans should pay for the cost of the British troops in America. Townshend promised to find new source of revenue in America. This was called the new tax legislation also known as The Townshend Act of 1767. This tax had two goals: fiscal and political. The new tax consisted of taxing imports of paper, paint, glass, and tea. These taxes would increase to about 40,000 a year (Marshall, 1987).

By the time began the US War of Independence (also called the American Revolution) against Britain in April 1775, the inhabitants of the American colonies, mostly, not after independence: they simply wanted the British government has paid attention to their complaints. But over the course of the war, many became supportive of the idea to break free from British rule (Barlow, 1996).

During this time, many American people were angry with the British. Americans did agree into paying taxes to the Britain, because their military troops where in America, further more they did not had protection from the parliament. By the Americans paying these taxes, they requested to be treated like British citizens. They felt that the British could not be trusted. As a result of all the economic issues of the thirteen colonies against the British Empire, the American Revolutionary War began. This war was an important event that took place, and lead to the Declaration of Independence which is currently known as the fourth of July (Wills, 2002).

New reasons to seek independence from Britain arose at any time. In August 1775, King George III declared that the settlers were rebels and hired foreign troops to fight them. The British attacked the coast of Maine and caused major damage to Virginia. In January 1776,

Thomas Paine published a pamphlet called *Common sense* (common sense). The pamphlet called attention to the fact that the inhabitants of the colonies are being treated unfairly by the king. Many pamphlet copies were sold, and the proposal of independence was gaining more support (Marshall, 1987).

On June 7, Richard Henry Lee of Virginia asked the Continental Congress to examine the possibility of declaring independence from Britain. The Congress appointed a five-person committee to draft the formal declaration. The first draft text was written by Thomas Jefferson . Some modifications were suggested by other committee members: John Adams, Benjamin Franklin, Roger Sherman, and Robert R. Livingston (Wills, 2002).

Conclusion

On July 2, 1776, Congress accepted the suggestion of independence. Over the next two days, discussed the content of the statement and On July 4, the Declaration of Independence was accepted by the representatives of twelve states. The New York delegation leaned to eleven days later. The statement was first published in newspapers and read aloud to crowds gathered in cities throughout the colonies. Members of Congress signed the official document, written on parchment, on August 2. The paper first presents a list of complaints against the English king and then brings the Declaration of Independence itself. This was, and is where Americans celebrate independence and freedom, land of the free and home of the brave. The Declaration of Independence is an important aspect and event in American history and significant to all Americans because many people lost their lives in order to have independence and freedom.

References

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